

Robustness Of Two Factor Response Surface Designs Within Split-Plot Structure Against Missing Observations

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Abstract

In this paper we presents Minimaxloss criterion for fixed variance ratio, based on D-, G- and A-efficiency, and which accounts within-whole plot and sub plot singlemissing observations, for constructing two factor robust designs with in split-plot response surface designs structure that is robust to a single missing observation at different designs points for fixed variance ratio. A missing observation make the outputs of Response Surface Modal is difficult. Then comparison of the loss in the data due to a single missing values by numerically computations for A-optimality, D- optimality and G-optimality. In these situations the effect of missing observations will also be studied on the basis of graphical tools like, Variance Dispersion Graph (VDG).

Introduction

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) is an important area of designs of experiments useful for developing, improving, and optimizing processes (Myers *et al*, 2009). While applying RSM in agricultural and industrial experiments, the basic principle of randomization is not achievable in many situations. These situations normally occurs when input factors are differentiated with respect to any characteristic or objective, i.e., (i) one and more factors are applied to larger experimental material (called whole plots (and other applied to relatively small experimental material (subplots), (ii) one or more factors are hard/difficult/expensive-to-change and others are easy-to-change, and (iii) some factors need to estimate with greater precision as compare to others. All above experimental situations lead to split plot designs (SP designs) which allow two different randomization procedures for different groups of factors. This class of designs is also referred to 'Response Surface Designs with Restricted Randomization. Different randomizations produce two error terms, first relate to whole-plot and second are sub plot error that affects the performance of these designs. Central composite designs (CCD), Box-Behnken designs (BBD) and small composite design are more popular for fitting second order response surface (SORS) models. The experimental designs which work well in the presence of problems such as abnormal observations, missing values, incomplete experiment, and inadequate response surface model are known as robust designs.

Literature Review

Split plot designs (SP designs), were initially introduced to apply agricultural experiments and then gained popularity in industry related experiments. In recent years, these designs have got sufficient attention in literature. Letsinger *et al*. (1996) introduced RSM for the analysis of SP designs and suggested the generalized least squares for estimating SPRS models. Bingham & Sitter (1999) and Bingham *et al*. (2004) presented construction of 2^{k-p} SP designs using aberration criterion. Trinca & Gilmour (2001) proposed Multistratum designs constructed through a sequential method. Vining *et al*. (2005) introduced SP central composite designs (VKM CCD) and SP Box-Behnken designs (VKM BBD) by modifying central composite designs and Box-Behnken designs of completely randomized structure. These designs are the generalized form of split plot designs. Kulahci & Bisgaard (2005) explained a method to construct SP designs from Plackett-Burman designs. Yang (2007) derived some result to construct fractional factorial SP deigns with weak minimum aberration. Construction of D-optimal SP designs were also suggested using exchange algorithms by Goos & Vandebroek (2001, 2003, and 2004) and Jones and Goos (2007). Review of recent developments in the area of designs of SP experiments is given in Jones & Nachtsheim (2009). For parameter estimation of second-order SP response surface model, they discussed about some designs for which OLS and GLS estimators of model parameters are

equivalent and outlined some general necessary conditions for this property, called these designs as *equivalent-estimation SP designs*. They also provide a catalogue of VKM CCD and VKM BBD. Based on central composite and Box-Behnken designs, Parker et al. (2006, 2007a) suggested two methods for the construction of balanced equivalent-estimation SP designs, while Parker et al.(2007b) extended these methods to construct unbalanced equivalent-estimation SP designs. Liang (2005) adopted two graphical tools, Three-dimensional VDG and FDS, for SPRS designs.SP designs gained considerable attention, but robustness of these designs against missing observations got no attention except one article of Chukwu (2013). He investigated the loss of single missing observation relative to D-efficiency for CCD. Gandhi and Kumaran (2014) used RSM to optimize a bio diesel data study. He used these graphs to examined and compare different variations of CCD. Yakubu et al. (2014) studied the effect of missing observation on prediction capability and on precision of estimates for CCD in completely randomized structure (CRD). Srisuradetchai (2015) investigated the robustness of response surface designs in CRD against missing values. He also introduced some robust measures and developed an R-package. Iwundu (2017) studied the loss of one or two missing values in response surface designs relative to D-, A- and G-efficiency.

Methodology

Methodology of this research includes model and its properties for SORS designs, loss due to missing observations relative to different optimality criteria and sub-classes of designs to be studied.

Second Order Model for Split Plot Response Surface Designs

Consider a SP experiment with w number of whole plot factors and k number of subplot factors. Let $N = \sum_{i=1}^m n_i$ be the total number of runs in a design, where m is the available units for whole plots factors and n_i the size of i th whole plot. For balanced design $n_i = n$ then the general form of the model analyzing the data of this experiment.

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \boldsymbol{\delta} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \quad (1)$$

Where vector \mathbf{y} is of response of order $N \times 1$, \mathbf{X} is the $N \times p$ matrix of coefficients (model matrix), $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the $p \times 1$ vector of parameters, $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is the random vector of whole plot errors of order $N \times 1$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is the random vector of sub-plot errors.

The alternative general form of the model vector is given as.

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{x})' = [1 | z_1, \dots, z_w | x_1, \dots, x_k | z_1 z_2, \dots, z_{w-1} z_w | z_1 x_1, \dots, z_w x_k | x_1 x_2, \dots, x_{k-1} x_k | z_1^2, \dots, z_w^2 | x_1^2, \dots, x_k^2] \quad (2)$$

Here z and x represent for whole plot and subplot factors. In model (1), it is assumed that $\boldsymbol{\delta} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ has mean $\mathbf{0}$ and variance and covariance matrix.

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \sigma_{\boldsymbol{\delta}}^2 \mathbf{I} + \sigma_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^2 \mathbf{J}_b$$

The OLS estimator of parameter vector is $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{OLS} = (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{y}$ (3)

With $var_cov(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{OLS}) = (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}'\boldsymbol{\Sigma}\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}$. On the other hand, the generalized least square estimate is $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS} = (\mathbf{X}'\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}'\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{y}$ with $var_cov(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS}) = (\mathbf{X}'\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{X})^{-1}$.

The predicted mean response at any design point \mathbf{x}_0 is

$$\widehat{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \mathbf{x}_0' \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$$

Where \mathbf{x}_0 is the point in the design space.

$$var[\widehat{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}_0)] = \mathbf{x}_0' (\mathbf{X}'\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{X})^{-1} \mathbf{x}_0 \quad (4)$$

Class of Designs under Study

Vining et al (2005) presented a design methodology that allows the modification of standard second order RS designs (e.g. Central Composite Designs(CCD's) and Box-Behnken Designs (BBD)) to accommodate split-plot type experiments. They also developed the conditions for these designs that, if satisfied, allow the equivalence of OLS and GLS estimates of model parameters. Such designs are now called the equivalent estimation Designs. The central composite designs under split plot structure introduced by them were named as 'VKM CCD'. These designs have four categories of design points: factorial, whole-plot axial, sub-plot and center points. They constructed VKM CCD for $1 \leq wp \leq 4$ and $1 \leq sp \leq 4$.

Wesley (2006) presented the general expressions of information matrices, its inverse, determinant and trace for CCD and BBD structures. These expressions were quite difficult to understand and apply. Therefore, in this study, these expressions are modified for VKM CCD to further discuss the robustness of this class of designs.

The modified expressions of information matrix along with some critical functions are given as:

$$(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{X}) = \begin{bmatrix} \Pi & 0 & \Delta_1(f_w + 2r_w\beta^2)\mathbf{J}'_{wp} & \Delta_1(f + 2r_s\alpha^2)\mathbf{J}'_{sp} \\ 0 & \text{Diag}(d_i) & 0 & 0 \\ \Delta_1(f_w + 2r_w\beta^2)\mathbf{J}'_{wp} & 0 & \Delta_1(2r_w\beta^4\mathbf{I}_{wp} + f)_w [\mathbf{J}'_{wp}\mathbf{J}'_{wp}] & \Delta_1 f [\mathbf{J}'_{sp}\mathbf{J}'_{wp}] \\ \Delta_1(f + 2r_s\alpha^2)\mathbf{J}'_{sp} & 0 & \Delta_1 f [\mathbf{J}'_{wp}\mathbf{J}'_{wp}] & (\Delta_2 2r_s\alpha^4)\mathbf{I}_{sp} + (\Delta_1 f + \Delta_3 2r_s\alpha^4) [\mathbf{J}'_{sp}\mathbf{J}'_{sp}] \end{bmatrix}$$

Notation and Critical Function of variance ratio (η) and whole plot sizes for balanced VKM CCD are given below:

CRITICAL FUNCTIONS:

Following are the critical functions for balanced VKM CCD:

$\Delta_1 = \frac{(1 + \eta)}{(1 + w_1 \eta)}$	$\Delta_2 = (1 + \eta)$	$\Delta_3 = -2 \left[\frac{\eta(1 + \eta)}{(1 + w_1 \eta)} \right]$
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Where

F	# of factorial runs (2^k or 2^{k-M})	a_i	# of whole plots with size w_i
f_w	# of whole plot factorial runs	r_w	# of repeated whole plot axials
w_i	i^{th} whole plot size	r_s	# of repeated subplot axials
Wp	# of whole plot factors	sp	# of subplot factors

In the above information matrix, '0' are given matrices of zeros of suitable size, J_{wp} and J_{sp} are unite vectors and I_{wp} and I_{sp} are identity matrices of order wp and sp . The matrix $Diag(d_i)$ has the diagonal elements.

$$d_i = \Delta_1 (f_w + 2r_w \beta^2)^2 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq wp$$

$$= \Delta_2 (f + 2r_s \alpha^2) \text{ for } wp+1 \leq i \leq k, \text{ where } k = wp + sp$$

$$= \Delta_1 f_w \text{ for } k+1 \leq i \leq k + \binom{wp}{2}$$

$$= \Delta_2 f \text{ for } k + \binom{wp}{2} + 1 \leq i \leq k + \binom{wp}{2} + wp \times sp + \binom{sp}{2}$$

Similarly, Π is the scalar quantity ($\Pi = N\Delta_1$) and for a balanced design $N = \sum_{i=1}^4 a_i w_i$
The information matrix maybe characterize as:

$$(X'R^{-1}X) = C = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} \end{bmatrix} C_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} \Pi & 0 \\ 0 & Diag(d_i) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_{12} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta_1 (f_w + 2r_w \beta^2) J'_{wp} & \Delta_1 (f + 2r_s \alpha^2) J'_{sp} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; C_{21} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta_1 (f_w + 2r_w \beta^2) J'_{wp} & 0 \\ \Delta_1 (f_w + 2r_s \alpha^2) J'_{wp} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_{22} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta_1 (2r_w \beta^4 I_{wp} + f_w) [J_{wp} J'_{wp}] & \Delta_1 f [J_{sp} J'_{wp}] \\ \Delta_1 f [J_{sp} J'_{wp}] & (\Delta_2 2r_s \alpha^4) I_{sp} + (\Delta_1 f + \Delta_3 2r_s \alpha^4) [J_{sp} J'_{sp}] \end{bmatrix}$$

Determinant of Information matrix for VKM CCD:

Using the analytical expressions, the determinant of information matrix ($X'R^{-1}X$) for VKM CCD is given as:

$$|X'R^{-1}X| = \frac{\Pi \Delta_1 (f_w + 2r_w \beta^2)^{wp} \left[\Delta_2 (f_w + 2r_s \alpha^2)^{sp} (\Delta_1 f_w)^{cw} (\Delta_2 f_w) \right]^{c+cs}}{\left[\frac{1 - \lambda_4 wp}{\Delta_1 2r_w \beta^4} \right] \left[\frac{1}{\Delta_1 2r_w \beta^4} \right]^{wp-1} \left[\frac{1 - \lambda_6 sp}{\Delta_2 2r_s \alpha^4} \right] - \left[\frac{\Delta_1 2r_w \beta^4 (\lambda_5)^2 wp sp}{1 - \lambda_4 wp} \right] * \left(\frac{1}{\Delta_1 2r_s \alpha^4} \right)^{sp-1}}$$

Where $c = (wp * sp)$, $cw = \binom{wp}{2}$ and $cs = \binom{sp}{2}$.

In order to find the effect of missing/lost values, partition the y vector and X matrix of eq. (5.1.1.) as

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_m \\ \dots \\ y_r \end{pmatrix} \text{ And } \begin{pmatrix} X_m \\ \dots \\ X_r \end{pmatrix}$$

Loss in Efficiencies Due to Missing Observations

In order to find loss due to missing values, brief description of optimality criteria is given below:

Loss due to Missing Observations in D-efficiency

In this section we find the loss of D-efficiency when some values are missed in experimental design and the parameters of corresponding model are estimated with generalized least square estimation.

- Loss in D-efficiency

$$l_1 = 1 - \frac{|X'_r R_r^{-1} X_r|}{|X'R^{-1}X|} \tag{5}$$

Loss due to Missing Observations in G-efficiency

In this section we find the loss of G-efficiency when some values are missed in experimental design.

- Loss in G-efficiency

$$l_2 = 1 - \frac{\text{Max}_{x_0 \in R} \text{SPV}}{(\text{Max}_{x_0 \in R} \text{SPV})_r} \quad (6)$$

Loss due to Missing Observations in A-efficiency

In this section we find the loss of A-efficiency when some values are missed in experimental designs.

- Loss in A-efficiency

$$l_3 = 1 - \frac{\text{trace}(X'R^{-1}X)^{-1}}{\text{trace}(X_r'R_r^{-1}X_r)^{-1}} \quad (7)$$

Graphical Tools

In above discussion, design comparison was based on single number optimality criteria to compare competing designs. For instance when the practitioner is interested in predicting and wants to learn more about prediction variance distribution, if the prediction variance is stable in the entire design region.

Giovannitti-Jensen and Myers (1989) introduced the variance dispersion graph (VDG) to compute the prediction variance properties of response surface designs. It displays the distribution of scaled prediction variance (SPV) throughout a multidimensional region on two-dimensional graphs.

Goldfarb et al. (2004) developed three-dimensional VDGs to evaluate prediction variance of mixture-process experiments. The conventional two-dimensional VDGs considered only a summary of the combined spaces. For mixture experiments with process variables, the design spaces can be thought of as combinations of two sub spaces.

Results and Discussions

Two-factors VKM CCD [whole-plot factor = 1 and subplot factor = 1] VKM CCD (1,1)

In VKM CCD (1,1), there are $N = 12$ total design points, out of which four are of factorial, four points are of axial of whole plots, two are axial of subplots and two points at center. Model matrix X and correlation matrix R are constructed in MS Excel and imported in MATLAB program as input matrices and arranged.

For Two-factors VKM CCD (1, 1), X matrix and correlation matrix R_i is given as

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -b & 0 & 0 & b^2 & 0 \\ 1 & -b & 0 & 0 & b^2 & 0 \\ 1 & b & 0 & 0 & b^2 & 0 \\ 1 & b & 0 & 0 & b^2 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -a & 0 & 0 & a^2 \\ 1 & 0 & a & 0 & 0 & a^2 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad R_i = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \frac{\eta}{1+\eta} \\ \frac{\eta}{1+\eta} & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Information Matrix for VKM CCD(1, 1) is given as:

$$(X'R^{-1}X) = \begin{bmatrix} \Pi & \mathbf{0} & \frac{4(1+\beta^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & \frac{2(2+\alpha^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} \\ \mathbf{0} & \text{Diag}(d_i) & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \frac{4(1+\beta^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{4(1+\beta^4)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & \frac{4(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} \\ \frac{2(2+\alpha^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{4(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & \frac{2(2+\alpha^4)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} \end{bmatrix}$$

For this design,

$f = 4$	$r_s = 2$	$\Delta_1 = \frac{(1+\eta)}{(1+2\eta)}$
$f_w = 4$	$r_w = 2$	$\Delta_2 = (1+\eta)$

wp = 1	w _i = 2	$\Delta_3 = -2 \left[\frac{\eta(1+\eta)}{(1+2\eta)} \right]$
sp = 1	N=12	

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi &= N\Delta_1 = \frac{12(1+\eta)}{(1+2\eta)} \\ d_1 &= \frac{4(1+\beta^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} \\ d_2 &= 2(2+\alpha^2)(1+\eta) \\ d_3 &= 4(1+\eta)\end{aligned}$$

Partitioning of the above information matrix for VKM CCD(1, 1) is given below

$$(X'R^{-1}X) = B = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$B_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} \Pi & 0 \\ 0 & \text{Diag}(d_i) \end{bmatrix} B_{12} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{4(1+\beta^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & \frac{2(2+\alpha^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B_{21} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{4(1+\beta^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & 0 \\ \frac{2(2+\alpha^2)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & 0 \end{bmatrix} B_{22} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{4(1+\beta^4)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & \frac{4(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} \\ \frac{4(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} & \frac{2(2+\alpha^4)(1+\eta)}{1+2\eta} \end{bmatrix}$$

Determinant of information matrix for VKM CCD (1,1)

The general expressions for the determinant of information matrix of VKM CCD (1, 1) is given as follows:

$$|X'R^{-1}X| = \frac{512(1+\alpha^2)(2+\beta^2)(3\beta^4 - 4\alpha^2\beta^2(-1+\beta^2) + \alpha^4(4 - 4\beta^2 + 3\beta^4))(1+\eta)^6}{(1+2\eta)^4}$$

Loss due to Missing Observations in D-efficiency

In VKM CCD (1,1), there are N = 12 total design points, out of which four are of factorial, four points are of axial of whole plots, two are axial of subplots and two points at center. To find loss due relative to D-efficiency (l_1) from equation (5) are computed for each type of design points, for varied values of $\alpha/\beta = [0.5, 0.7, 0.9, 1.1, 1.3, 1.5, 1.7, 1.9, 2.1, 2.3, 2.5]$ and variance ratio (1, 5, and 10). The loss relative to D-efficiency is calculated for VKM CCD (1, 1) and arranged in the Table 1

- Loss in D-efficiency $l_1 = 1 - \frac{|X_r'R_r^{-1}X_r|}{|X'R^{-1}X|}$

Results in Table 1 Loss due to Missing Observations in D-efficiency and the figures below may be explained as for different values of variance ratio [1, 5, 10], $\alpha/\beta = [0.5, 0.7, 0.9, 1.1, 1.3, 1.5, 1.7, 1.9, 2.1, 2.3, 2.5]$ loss when missing one whole plot axial or one center point is smaller than that of other design points.

When VR is fixed in below figures, the loss of missing one factorial point shows decreasing trend, loss of WP axial and subplot axial point has increasing trend whereas loss due to one center point has some curvature for increasing values of α and β .

For this design VKM CCD (1, 1) in Table 1, Variance Ratio (VR) 1, the design with $\alpha/\beta = 1.5$ has minimum loss among the maximum losses and for VR 5 & 10, the designs with $\alpha/\beta = 1.9$ have minimum loss among maximum losses.

Overall, the design with VR=1 and $\alpha/\beta = 1.6$ is a Minimax loss VKM CCD (1, 1) relative to D-efficiency. This design may also called "VKM CCD (1, 1) robust to single missing observation relative to D-efficiency".

Table 1 Loss due to Missing Observations in D-efficiency

VR	α, β	Loss when missing one				Maximum Loss
		Factorial point	WP axial point	Subplot axial point	Center point	
1	0.5	0.93248	0.13639	0.27891	0.08333	0.93248
	0.7	0.88125	0.15008	0.33349	0.10384	0.88125
	0.9	0.82332	0.16167	0.38913	0.14087	0.82332
	1.1	0.75816	0.17155	0.44518	0.19537	0.75816
	1.3	0.69069	0.18286	0.51082	0.24205	0.69069
	1.5	0.63764	0.19627	0.58599	0.24618	0.63764**
	1.7	0.60480	0.20820	0.65460	0.21938	0.65460
	1.9	0.58402	0.21699	0.70905	0.18891	0.70905
	2.1	0.56874	0.22322	0.75131	0.16474	0.75131
	2.3	0.55629	0.22775	0.78473	0.14717	0.78473
	2.5	0.54570	0.23116	0.81178	0.13449	0.81178
5	0.5	0.94045	0.04546	0.16704	0.02777	0.94045
	0.7	0.89482	0.05002	0.24235	0.03461	0.89482
	0.9	0.84502	0.05389	0.32188	0.04695	0.84502
	1.1	0.7937	0.05718	0.39969	0.06512	0.79374
	1.3	0.74423	0.06095	0.47560	0.08068	0.74423
	1.5	0.70274	0.06542	0.54827	0.08206	0.70274
	1.7	0.67126	0.06940	0.61220	0.07312	0.67126
	1.9	0.64684	0.07233	0.66534	0.06297	0.66534*
	2.1	0.62691	0.07440	0.70909	0.05491	0.70909
	2.3	0.61021	0.07591	0.74534	0.04905	0.74534
	2.5	0.59604	0.07705	0.77564	0.04483	0.77564
10	0.5	0.94227	0.02479	0.14162	0.01515	0.94227
	0.7	0.89790	0.02728	0.22164	0.01888	0.89790
	0.9	0.84995	0.02939	0.30659	0.02561	0.84995
	1.1	0.80182	0.03119	0.38935	0.03552	0.80182
	1.3	0.75640	0.03324	0.46760	0.04401	0.75640
	1.5	0.71753	0.03568	0.53969	0.04476	0.71753
	1.7	0.68637	0.03785	0.60256	0.03988	0.68637
	1.9	0.66112	0.03945	0.65541	0.03434	0.66112*
	2.1	0.64014	0.04058	0.69950	0.02995	0.69950
	2.3	0.62246	0.04140	0.73639	0.02675	0.73639
	2.5	0.60748	0.04202	0.76743	0.02445	0.76743

*Minimaxloss for fixed variance ratio

**Overall Minimaxloss

At Variance ratio 1 At Variance ratio 5

AtVariance ratio 10

Loss due to Missing Observations in G-efficiency

In VKM CCD (1,1), there are N = 12 total design points, out of which four are of factorial, four points are of axial of whole plots, two are axial of subplots and two points at center. To find loss due relative to G-efficiency (l_2) from equation (6) are computed for each type of design points, for varied values of $\alpha/\beta=[0.5,0.7,0.9,1.1,1.3,1.5,1.7,1.9,2.1,2.3,2.5]$ and variance ratio (1,5,10). The loss relative to G-efficiency is calculated for VKM CCD (1, 1) and arranged in the following Table 2:

• **Loss in G-efficiency**
$$l_2 = 1 - \frac{Max_{x_0 \in RSPV}}{(Max_{x_0 \in RSPV})_r}$$

Results in Table 2 and the below figures may be explained as for different values of variance ratio [1,5,10], $\alpha/\beta=[0.5,0.7,0.9,1.1,1.3,1.5,1.7,1.9,2.1,2.3,2.5]$ loss when missing one whole plot axial or one center point is smaller than that of other design points. When VR is fixed, the loss of missing one factorial point shows increasing trend, loss of WP axial and subplot axial point has increasing trend whereas loss due to one center point has some curvature for increasing values of α and β .

For this design VKM CCD (1, 1) in Table 2, Variance Ratio(VR) 1, the design with $\alpha=\beta=1.5$ has minimum loss among the maximum losses and for VR 5 & 10 the designs with $\alpha=\beta=1.3$ have minimum loss among maximum losses. Overall, the design with VR 10 and $\alpha=\beta=1.3$ is a minimax loss VKM CCD (1, 1) relative to G-

efficiency. This design may also called “*VKM CCD (1, 1) robust to single missing observation relative to G-efficiency*”.

Table 2: Loss due to Missing Observations in G-efficiency

VR	α, β	Loss when missing one				Maximum Loss
		Factorial point	WP axial point	Subplot axial point	Center point	
1	0.5	0.91196	0.01077	0.01741	0.00044	0.91196
	0.7	0.84777	0.01833	0.03810	0.00225	0.84777
	0.9	0.77783	0.02782	0.14395	0.00629	0.77783
	1.1	0.70282	0.04191	0.30554	0.10571	0.70282
	1.3	0.49340	0.00082	0.34197	0.24204	0.49340
	1.5	0.29390	0.00040	0.48966	0.24619	0.48966*
	1.7	0.16518	0.00899	0.58891	0.07270	0.58899
	1.9	0.12195	0.00059	0.64799	0.00626	0.64799
	2.1	0.09372	0.00022	0.69507	0.00509	0.69507
	2.3	0.07489	0.00011	0.73316	0.00375	0.73316
	2.5	0.06169	0.00000	0.76457	0.00281	0.76457
5	0.5	0.82842	0.00398	0.00628	0.00022	0.82842
	0.7	0.72248	0.00684	0.01418	0.00084	0.72248
	0.9	0.62602	0.01047	0.03888	0.00243	0.62602
	1.1	0.47003	0.00208	0.05897	0.06511	0.47003
	1.3	0.03700	0.00033	0.00179	0.08069	0.08069*
	1.5	0.00132	0.00000	0.11169	0.08206	0.11169
	1.7	0.08422	0.00060	0.33024	0.05035	0.33024
	1.9	0.05958	0.00022	0.38262	0.00214	0.38262
	2.1	0.04444	0.00010	0.43099	0.00173	0.43099
	2.3	0.03472	0.00000	0.47553	0.00137	0.47553
	2.5	0.02814	0.00000	0.51640	0.00094	0.51640
10	0.5	0.73919	0.00222	0.00343	0.00011	0.73919
	0.7	0.60461	0.00374	0.00794	0.00048	0.60461
	0.9	0.49714	0.00584	0.01666	0.00136	0.49714
	1.1	0.28461	0.00107	0.00718	0.03542	0.28461
	1.3	0.00140	0.00010	0.00097	0.04406	0.04406**
	1.5	0.00074	0.00000	0.00031	0.04471	0.04471
	1.7	0.04687	0.00024	0.20904	0.03988	0.20904
	1.9	0.03581	0.00011	0.25267	0.00111	0.25267
	2.1	0.02638	0.00000	0.29190	0.00096	0.29190
	2.3	0.02038	0.00000	0.33011	0.00073	0.33011
	2.5	0.01651	0.00000	0.36714	0.00051	0.36714

**Minimaxloss for fixed variance ratio

**Overall Minimaxloss

At Variance ratio 1

At Variance ratio 5

At Variance ratio 10

Loss due to Missing Observations in A-efficiency

In VKM CCD (1,1), there are N = 12 total design points, out of which four are of factorial, four points are of axial of whole plots, two are axial of subplots and two points at center. To find loss due relative to A-efficiency (l_3) from equation (7) are computed for each type of design points, for varied values of $\alpha/\beta=[0.5,0.7,0.9,1.1,1.3,1.5,1.7,1.9,2.1,2.3,2.5]$ and variance ratio (1,5, and 10). The loss relative to A-efficiency is calculated for VKM CCD (1, 1) and arranged in the following Table 3:

• **Loss relative to A-efficiency**
$$l_3 = 1 - \frac{trace(X'R^{-1}X)^{-1}}{trace(X'_rR_r^{-1}X_r)^{-1}}$$

Results in Table 3 and the figures below may give as for different values of variance ratio[1,5,10], $\alpha/\beta=[0.5,0.7,0.9,1.1,1.3,1.5,1.7,1.9,2.1,2.3,2.5]$ loss when missing one whole plot axial or one center point is smaller than that of other design points. When VR is fixed, the loss when missing one factorial point shows increasing trend, loss of WP axial and subplot axial point has decreasing trend whereas loss due to one center point has some curvature for increasing values of α and β .

For this design VKM CCD (1, 1) in Table 3, Variance Ratio(VR) 1,the design with $\alpha=\beta=1.9$ has minimum loss among the maximum losses and for VR 5 & 10, the designs with $\alpha=\beta=1.7$ have minimum loss among maximum losses. Overall, the design with VR (1) and $\alpha=\beta=1.1$ is a minimax loss VKM CCD (1, 1) relative to A-

efficiency. This design may also called “*VKM CCD (1, 1) robust to single missing observation relative to A-efficiency*”.

Table 3 Loss due to Missing Observations in A-efficiency

VR	α, β	Loss when missing one				Maximum Loss
		Factorial point	WP axial point	Subplot axial point	Center point	
1	0.5	0.17698	0.05345	0.14913	0.00978	0.17698
	0.7	0.24391	0.04696	0.13229	0.02263	0.24391
	0.9	0.24497	0.03579	0.10391	0.05715	0.24497
	1.1	0.19192	0.02346	0.07156	0.11693	0.19192
	1.3	0.12836	0.01585	0.05562	0.17264	0.17264
	1.5	0.10374	0.01489	0.07151	0.18389	0.18389
	1.7	0.11753	0.01614	0.10055	0.16207	0.16207
	1.9	0.14238	0.01670	0.12520	0.13587	0.14238*
	2.1	0.16459	0.01639	0.14314	0.11555	0.16459
	2.3	0.18163	0.01559	0.15647	0.10130	0.18163
	2.5	0.19428	0.014591	0.16696	0.09140	0.19428
5	0.5	0.07640	0.017041	0.04896	0.00315	0.07640
	0.7	0.11307	0.015198	0.04483	0.00746	0.11307
	0.9	0.11732	0.011682	0.03618	0.01925	0.11732
	1.1	0.09151	0.007581	0.02512	0.03959	0.09151
	1.3	0.06056	0.005049	0.01950	0.05862	0.06056
	1.5	0.04900	0.004725	0.02512	0.06329	0.06329
	1.7	0.05616	0.005164	0.03568	0.05708	0.05708*
	1.9	0.06911	0.005416	0.04511	0.04913	0.06911
	2.1	0.08114	0.005393	0.05247	0.04285	0.08114
	2.3	0.09076	0.005202	0.05834	0.03841	0.09076
	2.5	0.09818	0.004927	0.06323	0.03530	0.09818
10	0.5	0.04460	0.00920	0.02660	0.00170	0.04460
	0.7	0.06741	0.00822	0.02453	0.00405	0.06741
	0.9	0.07058	0.00633	0.01990	0.01051	0.07058
	1.1	0.05488	0.00410	0.01383	0.02165	0.05488
	1.3	0.03614	0.00272	0.01073	0.03211	0.03614
	1.5	0.02921	0.00254	0.01384	0.03477	0.03477
	1.7	0.03356	0.00278	0.01971	0.03152	0.03356**
	1.9	0.04148	0.00293	0.02502	0.02728	0.04148
	2.1	0.04892	0.00293	0.02923	0.02392	0.04892
	2.3	0.05494	0.00283	0.03266	0.02154	0.05494
	2.5	0.05964	0.00269	0.03555	0.01988	0.05964

*Minimaxloss for fixed variance ratio

**Overall Minimaxloss

At Variance ratio 1 At Variance ratio 5

At Variance ratio 10

2D- and 3D-VDG for VKM CCD (1, 1)

Variance dispersion graph for 2D-VGD rotations for varied values of $\alpha/\beta=[0.5,0.7,0.9,1.1,1.3,1.5,1.7,1.9,2.1,2.3,2.5]$ and variance ratio (1,5,10), of designs points against the scaled prediction variance (SPV) is given below.

At Variance Ratio 1

At Variance Ratio 5

At Variance Ratio 10

Discussion:

The above 2D- and 3D-VGDs, in above figures, may be explained as:

- When a single observation missed in VKM CCD (1,1), the values of SPV at different values of variance ratio and α , β , has a curvature in 2D graphs.
- when $VR = 1$, the design with $\alpha=\beta=2.5$ shows the maximum SPV, i.e., 0.9202 whereas at $\alpha=\beta=1.1$, SPV has a minimum value 0.6514
- Similarly, when VR is 5 & 10, the minimum values (0.716, 0.731) of SPV are at $\alpha=\beta=1.1$ and 0.9 respectively, and have maximum values (0.9563, 0.9645) are at $\alpha=\beta=2.5$.
- Overall, the maximum SPV is minimum at $VR=1$, $\alpha=\beta=1.1$ and maximum at $VR=10$, $\alpha=\beta=2.5$.

Conclusion

In VKM CCD (1,1), there are $N = 12$ total design points, out of which four are of factorial, four points are of axial of whole plots, two are axial of subplots and two points at center. To find loss due relative to D-efficiency (l_1) from equation (5), G-efficiency (l_2) from equation (6) and A-efficiency (l_3) from equation (7) are computed for each type of design points, for varied values of $\alpha/\beta=[0.5,0.7,0.9,1.1,1.3,1.5,1.7,1.9,2.1,2.3,2.5]$ and variance ratio (1, 5, 10). In VKM CCD (1, 1), on the following parameters settings we get more efficient and robust design.

Summary of VKM CCD (1,1) Robust to Missing Single Observations

w	k	Criteria	Parameters of robust design			Comments
			Ratio	α	β	
1	1	D	1	1.6	1.6	Relative to D-efficient
		G	10	1.3	1.3	Relative to G-efficient
		A	1	1.1	1.1	Relative to A-efficient

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